

JURISPRUDENCE

INTERNATIONAL LEGAL REGULATION OF THE FIGHT AGAINST CYBERCRIME

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Abstract

This article examines certain problems of international legal regulation of the fight against crimes in the field of information technology. The purpose of this article is to analyze current international legal mechanisms to combat cybercrime. Cybercrimes, as well as crimes related to violations of information security, are mainly of an international nature due to the fact that they are carried out in the international information space using the global cross-border Internet. The article updates the issue of forming an international institutional mechanism in the field of combating cybercrimes

Keywords: international law, international information law, crimes in the field of information technology, information and communication technologies, the Internet, information security, cybercrimes.

The progressive development of ICT and globalization processes, together with positive processes, also include certain problems in the field of information security, in particular on the Internet. The Internet is one of the most significant and breakthrough achievements at the global level in the information sphere. In the modern world, the Internet makes it possible for individuals, society and states to exchange a wide variety of information online (in real time), including audio and video recordings. The Internet is not only a means of communication, but also a medium where people enter into various types of legal relationships.

At the same time, the emergence of information cyberspace also carries very significant threats. The widespread use of computer technologies in everyday life and the creation of global computer networks based on them, as an integral part of modern international financial and banking activities, creates preconditions that facilitate the commission of criminal acts, and often such crimes remain unpunished. The spread of computer viruses and child pornography, fraud with plastic payment cards, theft of funds from bank accounts, computer terrorism - this is not a complete list of such crimes, which have received the common name "cybercrime".

Despite existing international agreements in the field of informatization, international law on many issues does not keep up with the challenges that arise as a result of the use of information and communication technologies. Many experts point to such gaps in international information law [1]. The dynamic spread of cybercrime in the modern world creates the need to analyze existing and develop new international legal mechanisms for regulating the fight against cybercrime.

Obviously, the problem of using ICT for criminal and terrorist purposes is especially expressed due to the fact that information plays an important role in the functional activities of various important strategic objects in the different fields. Therefore, one of the most important problems of ensuring information security is

the fight against cybercrimes, the main goal of which is to carry out illegal information influence on various systems of government or financial management, or public consciousness, etc.

Information as a product of human consciousness is immaterial and can only exist within a material medium. It is necessary to distinguish between relations regarding information, information carrier and information available on a material medium. Based on the definition of the main features of the concept of "information," we believe that information is an intangible object, perceived by human consciousness, representing information about phenomena occurring in society and nature, and the process of transmitting specific information or facts to any subject [2].

The "cybercrime" includes any crime that is committed in the information environment and can be carried out from anywhere in the world using the Internet and, accordingly, a feature of the commission of cybercrimes is their transborder nature. The cross-border nature of cybercrime creates unique opportunities for criminals to commit their illegal actions. In addition, the constant development of ICT and emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence or 5G will contribute to a further high growth in opportunities for crimes in cyberspace.

One of the important conditions for an effective response to international computer crimes is the creation of an international system and a common international policy to combat cybercrimes. This issue is included in the agenda of a variety of influential international organizations and forums such as the UN, Council of Europe, EU, SCO and CIS.

The significance of cyberspace and the possibility of threats have been recognized by the UN and the international community, but to date it has not been possible to reach a single agreement on cybercrime. Within the framework of the UN in 1985 the document "Study on Security Concepts" [3] was published, and in the chapter of this document "Problems and Threats in In-

ternational Security” information threats were not mentioned. But the widespread use of the Internet, and at the same time the emergence of new threats in the cyber sphere, gave impetus to the development of resolutions in the field of preventing the use of information technologies for purposes incompatible with the objectives of ensuring international stability and security. The UN recognized the importance of ICT in 2000 in the Report of the High-Level Panel of Experts on Information and Communications Technology. The problem of cybercrime became the subject of discussion in a specially created working group of the 10th UN Congress on Crime Prevention and Punishment of Offenders, held in April 2000 [4].

In 2002, the UN adopted resolution 57/295, called “Use of information and communication technologies for development” [5]. The resolution confirmed the desire to develop a unified strategy in the field of ICT. It should be noted that on December 27, 2019, the UN General Assembly adopted a resolution on combating cybercrime entitled “Countering the use of information and communication technologies for criminal purposes” [6]. According to the document was established a special open-ended intergovernmental committee of experts representing all regions to develop an international convention on combating the use of ICTs for criminal purposes. The authors of the resolution emphasized the need for improved coordination and cooperation between states in combating the use of ICTs, including by responding to requests from developing countries for technical assistance in improving their national legislation and regulations.

Within the framework of the World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS), held under the auspices of the UN in Geneva in 2003 and in Tunis in 2005, the problems of combating cyberterrorism were identified. At the second stage of the WSIS in Tunisia in November 2005, two final documents were adopted: political (“Tunisian Commitment”) and legal (“Tunisian Agenda for the Information Society”). In paragraph 15 of the Tunisian Commitment, states officially recognize “the need to effectively counter the problems and threats arising from the use of ICTs for purposes that are incompatible with the objectives of maintaining international stability and security and may have a negative impact on the integrity of infrastructure within individual states to the detriment of their safety. It is necessary to prevent the abuse of information resources and technologies for criminal and terrorist purposes and respect human rights” [8].

The Tunis Agenda for the Information Society [7] identified the importance of prosecuting cybercrime, including cybercrimes committed within the jurisdiction of one country but having consequences in another, and called on governments, in collaboration with other stakeholders, to develop the necessary legislation to enable investigation and criminal prosecution of cybercrime, referring to existing international instruments (UNGA resolutions 55/63 and 56/121 on combating the criminal use of information technologies). Also, in paragraph 42 of the Tunisia Program, states confirmed that measures taken to ensure the stability and security of the Internet, to combat cybercrime and counter spam,

must ensure protection and compliance with the provisions on privacy and freedom of speech, which are contained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

It is necessary to emphasize the role of the international agreement “Okinawa Charter for the Global Information Society” adopted in 2000 in the fight against cybercrime. The Okinawa Charter for the Global Information Society specifically states: “The efforts of the international community aimed at developing the global information society must be accompanied by concerted efforts to create a safe and crime-free cyberspace” [9].

Within the framework of the Council of Europe, the development of an international legal framework has been carried out for more than 30 years. From 1985 to 1989, the Separate Committee of Experts on Computer Crimes of the Council of Europe worked on the problem of computer crimes. Based on the results of the committee’s work, the Council of Europe adopted recommendation No. 11(89)9 of September 13, 1989, the content of which is largely similar to the document of the OECD committee discussed above. The document offered only lists of actions that constitute cybercrimes, but did not define the general concept of a crime in the cyber sphere. The first significant international agreement adopted within the Council of Europe is the Convention on Computer Crime, which was adopted in Budapest on November 23, 2001 and entered into force on July 1, 2004[10]. The document was drawn up by the Council of Europe in Strasbourg (France), with the active participation of the Council of Europe observer states of Canada, Japan, the Philippines, South Africa, and the USA [11].

It should be noted that the main direction of the Convention is to activate the fight against cybercrime, which stipulates intensive cooperation between law enforcement agencies of different states, and provides law enforcement agencies of the participating states with broad powers. At the same time, many experts believe that the broad powers granted to law enforcement agencies may cause some difficulties for states with liberal legislation to join the Convention.

On January 28, 2003, in Strasbourg (France), the Additional Protocol to the Convention on Computer Crime was adopted to criminalize offenses related to racism and xenophobia committed through computer systems, which entered into force on March 1, 2006.[12] According to Article 2 of the Additional Protocol, racist and xenophobic material means any written material, any image or any other representation of ideas or theories that promotes, promotes or incites hatred, discrimination or violence against any person or group of persons, if as a pretext factors based on race, color, national or ethnic origin, and religion are used.

On May 15, 2022, the Second Additional Protocol to the Cybercrime Convention, concerning enhanced cooperation and disclosure of electronic evidence, was adopted in Strasbourg (France).[13] The Second Additional Protocol to the Cybercrime Convention provides a legal framework for the disclosure of domain name registration information and for direct cooperation with service providers regarding subscriber information, effective means of obtaining subscriber information and traffic data, immediate cooperation in emergency situations, mutual assistance tools, as well as guarantees for the protection of personal data.

Within the CIS, the first international agreement in the fight against cybercrime is the Agreement on Cooperation of Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States in the Combating Crimes in the Sphere of Computer Information, adopted on June 1, 2001 in Minsk. The agreement defined concepts such as “computer crime,” “computer information,” “malware,” and “illegal access.” This agreement ceased to apply on the date of entry into force of the Agreement on Cooperation of the Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States in the Combating Crimes in the Field of Information Technology dated September 28, 2018, which was concluded in Dushanbe [14]. The purpose of the agreement is cooperation between the participating countries in order to ensure an effective fight against crimes in the field of information technology, and the desire to create a legal basis for cooperation between law enforcement agencies of the Parties in the fight against crimes in the field of information technology. The document defines such concepts as malicious program “information technology”, “information system”, “computer information”, “unauthorized access to information”.

Since 2006, within the SCO there has been a group of experts from member states of the Organization for International Information Security, which is a permanent body of the SCO and works to coordinate relevant ministries and departments. In turn, the foundation for cooperation between the SCO countries in the field of information security is the intergovernmental Agreement on cooperation in the field of ensuring international information security, signed on June 16, 2009 [15]. In November 2020, a Joint Statement of the Heads of SCO Member States on cooperation in the field of ensuring international information security was adopted. In 2021, following the results of the SCO anniversary summit in Dushanbe, a Plan for interaction between the SCO countries on ensuring international information security for 2022-2023, developed with the active participation of Uzbekistan, was signed. Currently, all SCO countries, without exception, are implementing national strategic and conceptual documents aimed at developing a digital society, transferring public administration, the financial and economic sector to a digital format.

In our opinion, in order to eliminate numerous international legal conflicts caused by the cross-border nature of cybercrimes, it is necessary to develop a universal international agreement in the fight against cybercrimes, containing provisions regarding the relationship and priority between international and national principles and norms, especially regarding liability for cybercrimes. It follows from this that the development of a Single International Agreement within the UN will have to contribute not only to the effective coordination of the actions of states in the fight against cybercrimes, but also to the formation of an international institutional mechanism in the field of interstate cooperation to combat cybercrimes.

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